

STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF DIFFICULT CONCEPTS IN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL CORE SUBJECTS IN MATHEMATICS: BASIS FOR DEVELOPING ENHANCED INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates senior high school students' perceptions of difficult concepts in core Mathematics subjects to guide the development of an enhanced intervention program. Employing a quantitative survey design, the researchers gathered data using a validated and pilot-tested questionnaire administered to 293 Grade 12 students selected through stratified random sampling from the 1,231-student population of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for the School Year 2024–2025. Weighted mean, chi-square, and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient were used to analyze the perceived level of difficulty across the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and to determine relationships between perceptions across sex, tracks, and strands. Results revealed that students consistently identified several concepts in General Mathematics—such as rational, exponential, and logarithmic functions, as well as logical propositions—as difficult, while in Statistics and Probability, the most challenging topics included sampling distributions, Central Limit Theorem applications, hypothesis testing, and correlation and regression analysis. A strong positive correlation was found between male and female students' perceptions, whereas students from different tracks and strands showed weak and non-significant correlations. Findings also indicated that large class sizes, incomplete learning competencies, lack of independent practice, and prior mathematics difficulties contributed to learning challenges. The study emphasizes the necessity of targeted instructional strategies and teacher training to address these gaps and improve mathematical understanding.

Keywords: *MELC, perception, intervention programs, core subjects*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, the Senior High School Curriculum comprises the core, applied, and specialized subjects defined in the succeeding sentences. Core subjects ensure that learners will be equipped with the competencies required for specialization studies regardless of the chosen strand. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), as these subjects are compulsory, the mathematics-related core subjects are as important as other subjects according to the implementation of basic education. Core subjects are composed of various fundamental subject areas.

In the 11th Grade of Senior High School at the Schools Division of Cavite Province, mathematics-related core subjects in all strands are General Mathematics and Statistics and Probability. General Mathematics is a subject that deals with solving problems involving rational, exponential, and logarithmic functions, solving business-related problems, and applying logic to real-life situations. Moreover, Statistics and Probability deals with finding the mean and variance of a random variable, applying sampling techniques and distributions, estimating population mean and proportion, performing hypothesis testing on population mean and proportion, and performing correlation and regression analyses on real-life problems.

According to the statistical report released by the Office of the School Registrar about Grade 12 Enrollees for School Year 2024-2025 of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, there were 1,239 Grade Eleven (11) and 1,231 Grade Twelve (12) students, a total of 2,470 learners enrolled across tracks, strands, and specializations. A great number of learners are admitted heterogeneously in terms of their intellectual level at the opening of the school year.

According to Tabao & Faiz (2020), students may not yet fully decide about the nature of Mathematics because they are not sure of their confidence in doing Mathematics work, and some still view it as a hard and complicated subject, as the study revealed. Lacking skills in these areas can lead to students struggling to learn the concepts and ideas being taught. In learning mathematics, there are also many lessons to be remembered, which is why memorization comes along the way. However, many humans can only remember 10% of what they hear, 20% of what they read, and 80% of what they see (iDashboard UK, 2018). This caused students to have trouble learning lessons with a scientific approach. In addition, English is used as the medium of language in this subject. Difficulty in understanding could also be one reason. Filipino students were concluded to be poor in English grammar and proficiency, as the curriculum for said courses has been changed (Pachina, n.d.).

This suggests that not all students from Angelo Levardo Loyola Senior High School perform well or pass, particularly in mathematics-related subjects, even STEM students who are considered to belong to average to above-average groups of learners struggle to grasp the fundamentals of the subject.

Literature Review

The increasing emphasis on mathematics in senior high school curricula underscores its significance as a core subject for developing analytical and problem-solving skills. However, many students perceive mathematics as a challenging discipline, with certain concepts deemed particularly difficult to grasp. Understanding these perceptions is critical for developing intervention programs that address learning gaps and foster academic achievement. This review of related literature examines previous studies on students' perceptions of difficult mathematical concepts, their implications for learning, and strategies for intervention.

Students' Perception of Mathematics

Numerous studies have explored students' attitudes toward mathematics, often highlighting a prevalent perception of the subject as difficult and intimidating. According to the study of Blessing (2024), self-efficacy influences motivation, study habits, and attitudes toward mathematics, thereby shaping overall academic outcomes. Factors contributing to these perceptions include the abstract nature of mathematical concepts, inadequate foundational knowledge, and teaching methodologies that fail to cater to diverse learning styles.

In the context of senior high school, students often encounter advanced topics such as algebra, trigonometry, calculus, and statistics. A study by Estonanto and Dio (2019) revealed that abstract mathematical concepts of Calculus, the teaching style and attitude of the teacher, and the poor comprehension and analytical skills of the students were the major factors that caused the mathematics anxiety of the participants. These difficulties are compounded by cognitive and emotional barriers, such as math anxiety and lack of motivation.

Core Concepts in Senior High School Mathematics

Research has identified specific areas in senior high school mathematics that students perceive as particularly challenging. For instance, several studies have found that algebraic and trigonometry-related topics such as quadratic equations and trigonometric functions are frequently perceived as difficult by senior-high students because they are abstract and depend heavily on prior knowledge (Imasuen & Omoni, 2024). Similarly, Didis and Erbas (2015) emphasized that students have difficulties in solving both symbolic quadratic equations and quadratic word problems, they performed better in the context of symbolic equations compared with word problems. Student difficulties in solving symbolic problems were mainly associated with arithmetic and algebraic manipulation errors.

In the study of Olofinlae and Jimoh (2019), it was recommended amongst others that workshops should be organized to train mathematics teachers on the effectiveness and efficient strategies that should be adopted for the teaching of the identified difficult mathematics concepts.

The difficulty of these concepts often leads to poor academic performance and diminished confidence, creating a cycle of disengagement. This underscores the importance of targeted interventions to address these challenges effectively.

Synthesis

The literature analysis highlights the complex difficulties senior high school math students encounter in comprehending fundamental ideas. According to important research, students frequently view mathematics as a challenging and frightening subject because of its abstract character, the intricacy of certain of its topics, and a lack of fundamental knowledge. Due in significant part to their dependence on symbolic representations and links to previously learned material, concepts like algebra, trigonometry, probability, and calculus are commonly recognized as difficult subjects.

Students' attitudes and performance in mathematics are also greatly impacted by psychological issues including math anxiety and low self-efficacy. These emotional obstacles frequently result in disengagement, which exacerbates learning challenges. Because traditional lecture-based approaches are unable to fulfill the different demands of learners, instructional methodologies play an especially important role. Rather, technology use, collaborative learning, and differentiated instruction have been emphasized as successful ways to improve comprehension and engagement.

Research highlights the significance of intervention plans designed to close certain learning gaps. Regular evaluations, prompt feedback, and creative techniques to fill conceptual gaps are all incorporated into successful programs. It has been demonstrated that integrating technology, such as dynamic geometry software, may provide dynamic and captivating learning experiences that simplify difficult subjects.

Despite these insights, limitations in the existing body of research, such as reliance on self-reported data and the contextual specificity of findings, call for further exploration. Future studies should adopt mixed-method approaches and longitudinal designs to deepen understanding and improve generalizability.

Overall, the literature highlights the need for a comprehensive intervention program that addresses both cognitive and emotional challenges in learning mathematics. By combining targeted instructional strategies, supportive learning environments, and advanced tools, such programs can foster mathematical proficiency and positive attitudes among senior high school students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the students' perception of difficult concepts in senior high school core subjects in Mathematics at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for School Year 2024-2025. It also identified reasons that affect the difficulties experienced by senior high school learners in mathematics-related subject areas.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the most essential learning competencies perceived as difficult by senior high school students in terms of the following core subjects in Mathematics:
 - a. General Mathematics; and
 - b. Statistics and Probability?
2. What are the causes of the difficulties experienced by senior high school students in core subjects in Mathematics?
3. Is there any significant relationship between the topics of core subjects in Mathematics perceived by the following:
 - a. male and female students; and
 - b. students from different tracks and strands as difficult?

METHODOLOGY

A. Sampling

Cochran's Finite Population Correction was utilized as sampling size formula. The said formula is shown below:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{(n_0 - 1)}{N}}$$

where: n = sampling size
 n₀ = adjusted sample size
 N = population size

The Calculator

Precision Level: ±5% ▼

Confidence Level: 95% ▼

Estimated Proportion: 0.5 ▼

Small Population:

Population Size: 1231

The appropriate sample size given the population size and specified combination of precision, confidence and variability is 293.

Figure 1. Online calculator for determining sampling size using Cochran's Finite Population Correction

B. Data Collection

The following steps are considered to be followed in data gathering in order to complete the study:

Research instrument from the study of Amedenu (2017) will be adapted and modified by the researchers. It underwent validity and reliability tests under the careful examination of a registered psychometrician. After, pilot testing and re-testing to refine the research instrument will be done.

Prior to the administration of the questionnaire, a request letter to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Carmona seeking for the approval to conduct the proposed study will be sent. A request letter also will be sent to the School Head of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School asking for the administration of survey questionnaire to the target participants of the study.

Informed consent was provided for respondents whose age are 18 years old above or parental consent for the parents of the participants whose age are 18 years old below. Their willingness to participate the study will be sought. Data privacy was given emphasis in the data gathering process. Upon the consent of the respondents, nature of the study was explained prior to the distribution of questionnaires.

Any inquiry or question regarding with the items in the survey questionnaire was addressed. After answering the questionnaire, data was tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

C. Plan for Data Analysis

To be able to analyze the data collected through a questionnaire, the following statistical tools were utilized:

Frequency. It is the actual response to a specific item or question in the questionnaires where the respondents check his/her choice.

Weighted Mean. The weighted mean is a type of mean that is calculated by multiplying the weight associated with a particular event or outcome with its associated quantitative outcome and then summing all the products together. In other words, when some values weigh more than the others that's when the weighted mean is calculated.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum w_i x_i}{\sum w_i}$$

Whereas:

\bar{x} = weighted mean
 W_i = allocated weight value
 X_i = observed value

The data was analyzed using weighted mean for identifying difficult topics and possible causes of the perceived difficulty as criterion set will be adopted from the study of Amedenu (2017).

Chi-square. When the sample sizes are large, a chi-squared test is a statistical hypothesis test used in the analysis of contingency tables. To put it another way, the main purpose of this test is to determine whether two categorical variables have independent effects on the test statistic.

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Whereas:

- χ^2 = chi squared
- O_i = observed value
- E_i = expected value

Spearman correlation coefficient. It is also known as Spearman's rho or Spearman's rank correlation. Usually, it is indicated by the Greek letter rho (ρ). Spearman's rho measures the degree of association between two variables, like all correlation coefficients do. This will measure the correlation between concepts perceived by male and female, and students from different tracks and strand as difficult.

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Whereas:

- ρ = Spearman's rank correlation coefficient
- d_i = difference between the two ranks of each observation
- n = number of observations

RESULTS

Table 1. Perception of Senior High School Students in the Difficulty of Concepts in General Mathematics

Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in General Mathematics	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
represents real-life situations using functions, including piece-wise functions	2.14	Not Difficult
evaluates a function	1.95	Not Difficult
performs addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and composition of functions	2.05	Not Difficult
solves problems involving functions	2.53	Not Difficult
represents real-life situations using rational functions	3.91	Difficult

distinguishes rational function, rational equation, and rational inequality	1.93	Not Difficult
solves rational equations and inequalities	2.93	Not Difficult
represents a rational function through its: (a) table of values, (b) graph, and (c) equation	4.67	Difficult
finds the domain and range of a rational function	2.40	Not Difficult
determines the: (a) intercepts; (b) zeroes; and (c) asymptotes of rational functions	2.53	Not Difficult
solves problems involving rational functions, equations, and inequalities	2.76	Not Difficult
represents real-life situations using one-to one functions	2.49	Not Difficult
determines the inverse of a one-to-one function	2.04	Not Difficult
represents an inverse function through its: (a) table of values, and (b) graph	2.52	Not Difficult
finds the domain and range of an inverse function	2.18	Not Difficult
solves problems involving inverse functions	2.57	Not Difficult
represents real-life situations using exponential functions	4.49	Difficult
distinguishes between exponential function, exponential equation, and exponential inequality	1.96	Not Difficult
solves exponential equations and inequalities	3.81	Difficult
represents an exponential function through its: (a) table of values, (b) graph, and (c) equation	4.30	Difficult
finds the domain and range of an exponential function	2.59	Not Difficult
determines the intercepts, zeroes, and asymptotes of an exponential function	2.81	Not Difficult
solves problems involving exponential functions, equations, and inequalities	2.51	Not Difficult
represents real-life situations using logarithmic functions	3.55	Difficult
distinguishes logarithmic function, logarithmic equation, and logarithmic inequality	2.13	Not Difficult
solves logarithmic equations and inequalities	2.24	Not Difficult
represents a logarithmic function through its: (a) table of values, (b) graph, and (c) equation	4.14	Difficult
finds the domain and range of a logarithmic function	3.99	Difficult
determines the intercepts, zeroes, and asymptotes of logarithmic functions	4.09	Difficult

solves problems involving logarithmic functions, equations, and inequalities	3.98	Difficult
illustrates simple and compound interests	2.04	Not Difficult
distinguishes between simple and compound interests	2.08	Not Difficult
computes interest, maturity value, future value, and present value in simple interest and compound interest environment	2.67	Not Difficult
solves problems involving simple and compound interests	2.38	Not Difficult
illustrates simple and general annuities	1.40	Not Difficult
distinguishes between simple and general annuities	2.15	Not Difficult
finds the future value and present value of both simple annuities and general annuities	2.43	Not Difficult
calculates the fair market value of a cash flow stream that includes an annuity	3.58	Difficult
calculates the present value and period of deferral of a deferred annuity	2.43	Not Difficult
illustrate stocks and bonds	1.88	Not Difficult
distinguishes between stocks and bonds	2.39	Not Difficult
describes the different markets for stocks and bonds	1.59	Not Difficult
analyzes the different market indices for stocks and bonds	2.19	Not Difficult
illustrates business and consumer loans	1.90	Not Difficult
distinguishes between business and consumer loans	1.97	Not Difficult
solves problems involving business and consumer loans (amortization, mortgage)	2.62	Not Difficult
illustrates and symbolizes propositions	1.87	Not Difficult
distinguishes between simple and compound propositions	2.30	Not Difficult
performs the different types of operations on propositions	3.87	Difficult
determines the truth values of propositions	4.02	Difficult
illustrates the different forms of conditional propositions	4.50	Difficult
illustrates different types of tautologies and fallacies	3.92	Difficult
determines the validity of categorical syllogisms	2.66	Not Difficult
establishes the validity and falsity of real-life arguments using logical propositions, syllogisms, and fallacies	2.37	Not Difficult

Table 1 implies that “*represents a rational function through its: (a) table of values, (b) graph, and (c) equation*” is the most difficult concept in General Mathematics with a weighted mean of 4.67.

Table 2. Perception of Senior High School Students in the Difficulty of Concepts in Statistics & Probability

Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Statistics & Probability	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
illustrates a random variable (discrete and continuous)	1.95	Not Difficult
distinguishes between a discrete and a continuous random variable	1.40	Not Difficult
finds the possible values of a random variable	1.59	Not Difficult
illustrates a probability distribution for a discrete random variable and its properties	2.67	Not Difficult
computes probabilities corresponding to a given random variable	2.49	Not Difficult
illustrates the mean and variance of a discrete random variable	1.96	Not Difficult
calculates the mean and the variance of a discrete random variable	2.59	Not Difficult
interprets the mean and the variance of a discrete random variable	2.57	Not Difficult
solves problems involving mean and variance of probability distributions	2.38	Not Difficult
illustrates a normal random variable and its characteristics	2.24	Not Difficult
identifies regions under the normal curve corresponding to different standard normal values	2.52	Not Difficult
converts a normal random variable to a standard normal variable and vice versa	2.81	Not Difficult
computes probabilities and percentiles using the standard normal table	2.51	Not Difficult
illustrates random sampling	2.67	Not Difficult
distinguishes between parameter and statistic	2.38	Not Difficult
identifies sampling distributions of statistics (sample mean)	3.87	Difficult
finds the mean and variance of the sampling distribution of the sample mean	4.02	Difficult
defines the sampling distribution of the sample mean for normal population when the variance is: (a) known; (b) unknown	3.92	Difficult

illustrates the Central Limit Theorem	4.14	Difficult
defines the sampling distribution of the sample mean using the Central Limit Theorem	3.99	Difficult
solves problems involving sampling distributions of the sample mean	3.98	Difficult
illustrates the t-distribution	2.43	Not Difficult
identifies percentiles using the t-table	2.66	Not Difficult
identifies the length of a confidence interval	2.37	Not Difficult
computes for the length of the confidence interval	2.62	Not Difficult
computes for an appropriate sample size using the length of the interval	2.59	Not Difficult
solves problems involving sample size determination	2.81	Not Difficult
illustrates: (a) null hypothesis; (b) alternative hypothesis; (c) level of significance; (d) rejection region; and (e) types of errors in hypothesis testing	2.51	Not Difficult
identifies the parameter to be tested given a real-life problem	3.81	Difficult
formulates the appropriate null and alternative hypotheses on a population mean	2.76	Not Difficult
identifies the appropriate form of the test-statistic when: (a) the population variance is assumed to be known; (b) the population variance is assumed to be unknown; and (c) the Central Limit Theorem is to be used	4.68	Difficult
identifies the appropriate rejection region for a given level of significance when: (a) the population variance is assumed to be known; (b) the population variance is assumed to be unknown; and (c) the Central Limit Theorem is to be used	4.30	Difficult
computes for the test-statistic value (population mean)	4.50	Difficult
draws conclusion about the population mean based on the test-statistic value and the rejection region	2.76	Not Difficult
solves problems involving test of hypothesis on the population mean	3.91	Difficult
formulates the appropriate null and alternative hypotheses on a population proportion	2.14	Not Difficult
identifies the appropriate form of the test-statistic when the Central Limit Theorem is to be used	2.53	Not Difficult

identifies the appropriate rejection region for a given level of significance when the Central Limit Theorem is to be used	3.91	Difficult
computes for the test-statistic value (population proportion)	2.14	Not Difficult
draws conclusion about the population proportion based on the test-statistic value and the rejection region	1.95	Not Difficult
solves problems involving test of hypothesis on the population proportion	3.81	Difficult
illustrates the nature of bivariate data	2.38	Not Difficult
constructs a scatter plot	2.66	Not Difficult
describes shape (form), trend (direction), and variation (strength) based on a scatter plot	2.37	Not Difficult
calculates the Pearson's sample correlation coefficient	3.92	Difficult
solves problems involving correlation analysis	4.33	Difficult
identifies the independent and dependent variables	1.96	Not Difficult
calculates the slope and y-intercept of the regression line	3.55	Difficult
interprets the calculated slope and y-intercept of the regression line	2.43	Not Difficult
predicts the value of the dependent variable given the value of the independent variable	3.87	Difficult
solves problems involving regression analysis	4.02	Difficult

Table 2 implies that “*identifies the appropriate form of the test-statistic when: (a) the population variance is assumed to be known; (b) the population variance is assumed to be unknown; and (c) the Central Limit Theorem is to be used*” is the most difficult concept in Statistics & Probability with a weighted mean of 4.68.

Table 3. Causes of the Difficulties experienced by Senior High School students in Core subjects in Mathematics

Causes of Difficulty of Concept in Mathematics	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Mathematics teacher used discouraging words about the subject	2.14	Disagree
Class size was above 40	4.02	Agree
The learning competencies in the curriculum guide was not completed	3.92	Agree

I did not practice Mathematics on my own aside work given by teacher	4.14	Agree
I had Mathematics problem since junior high school	3.81	Agree
Mathematics subject is taught only for one semester	2.81	Disagree
My teacher had difficulty with some topics in Mathematics himself / herself	3.87	Agree
My teacher in Mathematics was not punctual	1.95	Disagree
Mathematics is the most difficult core subject in Senior High School	4.33	Agree
My teacher was not of my preferred gender	3.10	Agree

Table 3 shows that the students perceived Mathematics as the most difficult core subject in Senior High School with a highest weighted mean of 4.33 which means that it is the major cause of students having difficulty of concepts in Mathematics.

Table 4. Difficult Concepts of Core Subjects in Mathematics perceived by Male and Female Students

Core Subjects in Mathematics	r_s	p-value	Interpretation
General Mathematics	0.999	0.001	Statistically Significant
Statistics & Probability	0.669	0.035	Statistically Significant

Table 4 illustrates that using Spearman's rank-order correlation between Male and Female Senior High School Students, there was a strong, positive correlation in both General Mathematics and Statistics & Probability subjects, which would be considered statistically significant.

Table 5. Difficult Concepts of Core Subjects in Mathematics perceived by students from Different Tracks and Strands

Core Subjects in Mathematics	r_s	p-value	Interpretation
General Mathematics	-0.140	0.699	Not Statistically Significant
Statistics & Probability	0.173	0.631	Not Statistically Significant

Table 5 illustrates that using Spearman's rank-order correlation between students from different Tracks of Senior High School, there was a weak correlation in both General Mathematics and Statistics & Probability subjects, which would not be considered statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study provide a comprehensive view of the concepts in General Mathematics and Statistics & Probability that senior high school students perceive as difficult, as well as the underlying factors contributing to these challenges. In General Mathematics, students identified topics such as rational functions, exponential and logarithmic functions, and logical propositions as the most difficult. For instance, "representing a rational function through its table of values, graph, and equation" had the highest difficulty rating, suggesting that students struggle with multi-representational understanding. This aligns with the findings of Didis and Erbas (2015), who reported that students commonly experience difficulty in symbolic manipulation and graphical interpretation due to the abstract nature of these concepts. The difficulty with logical propositions, tautologies, and fallacies is also consistent with Belbase (2013), who noted that students often struggle with abstract reasoning and logical structures, contributing to anxiety and disengagement.

In Statistics & Probability, topics involving sampling distributions, Central Limit Theorem (CLT), hypothesis testing, and correlation and regression were perceived as highly difficult, with "identifying the appropriate form of the test statistic when variance conditions vary" rated the most difficult. Additionally, the complexity of CLT and hypothesis testing reflects Fia's (2022) assertion that scientific and mathematical anxiety often stems from abstract and non-intuitive concepts.

The results further indicate a strong positive correlation between male and female students' perceptions of difficult concepts, implying that perceived difficulty transcends gender. This is consistent with Estonato and Dio's (2019) conclusion that mathematics anxiety and conceptual difficulty occur regardless of sex and are more closely linked to instructional and cognitive factors. However, the weak and statistically insignificant correlation across tracks and strands suggests that academic background influences perceived difficulty differently, possibly due to varied prior knowledge or strand-specific learning experiences.

Regarding causes of difficulty, students agreed that large class sizes, incomplete curriculum coverage, lack of self-practice, and long-standing struggles with mathematics contribute significantly to their challenges. This supports Potvin (2014), who argued that declining interest and difficulty in math often result from insufficient foundational skills and overcrowded learning environments. The finding that "Mathematics is the most difficult core subject in Senior High School" further reinforces Tabao and Faiz's (2020) claim that students often view mathematics as inherently complex due to its abstract content and language demands.

Overall, the study's findings are largely consistent with existing literature, particularly regarding the nature of difficult concepts, the influence of instructional factors, and the emotional and cognitive barriers students encounter. The results emphasize the need for targeted intervention programs, teacher training, and enhanced instructional materials—recommendations that align with Olofinlae and Jimoh's (2019) call for professional development focused on teaching strategies for difficult mathematics concepts. The consistency between the present findings and prior studies strengthens the validity of the conclusion that addressing both conceptual and contextual factors is essential for improving students' mathematics performance.

Conclusions

This study examined senior high school students' perceptions of difficult concepts in General Mathematics and Statistics & Probability, along with the factors contributing to these difficulties, in order to guide the development of an enhanced intervention program. The findings revealed that students consistently struggle with abstract and multi-representational competencies, particularly those involving rational, exponential, and logarithmic functions in General Mathematics, and sampling distributions, the Central Limit Theorem, hypothesis testing, and correlation and regression analysis in Statistics & Probability. These topics emerged as the most challenging among the Most Essential Learning Competencies.

The study also found that student difficulties stem from a combination of academic and contextual factors, including large class sizes, incomplete coverage of competencies, inadequate independent practice, and pre-existing weaknesses in foundational mathematical skills. These factors underscore the need for strengthened instructional approaches and targeted remediation.

With respect to the relationships among student groups, the results showed a strong positive correlation between male and female students' perceptions of difficult concepts, indicating that difficulty is experienced similarly regardless of sex. However, the weak and non-significant correlation across tracks and strands suggests that students' academic backgrounds influence their perceived challenges differently.

Overall, the study concludes that improving mathematics performance requires focused intervention on the most difficult concepts, enhanced teacher support, and sustained remediation efforts. The findings highlight the importance of responsive instructional practices and the need for further research to better understand and address the diverse learning needs of senior high school students.

Recommendations

In light of the study's findings, which revealed specific mathematical concepts students struggle with and several factors contributing to these difficulties, the following recommendations are proposed to help improve students' learning experiences and guide future efforts in enhancing Mathematics instruction.

1. Develop an Enhanced Intervention Program

Create targeted instructional materials and remediation activities focusing on the most difficult concepts identified in General Mathematics and Statistics & Probability, such as rational functions, logarithmic and exponential functions, sampling distributions, the Central Limit Theorem, and hypothesis testing.

2. Provide Professional Development for Mathematics Teachers

Conduct training sessions or workshops to strengthen teachers' strategies in simplifying abstract concepts, using technology for visualizations, and applying differentiated instruction to address diverse learner needs.

3. Implement Structured Support for Foundational Skills

Offer diagnostic assessments, remedial classes, and consistent practice exercises to help students address long-standing difficulties in mathematics, particularly those that began in junior high school.

4. Encourage Future Research with Broader or Different Approaches

Replicate the study in other schools or divisions, or use qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups to further explore students' reasoning and clarify unexpected findings, such as the weak correlation across tracks and strands.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

It was vital to address ethical concerns to ensure the safety, rights, and well-being of the research participants. The researchers secured the proper authorization for the study aimed at answering specific questions while honoring participants' autonomy. A primary ethical obligation was acquiring voluntary, informed consent. Parents and guardians were informed about the purpose and nature of the study and fully comprehended this information before they gave their consent.

Furthermore, for minor participants, the researchers obtained informed assent to verify their understanding of the study and their willingness to engage in it. Protecting confidentiality and anonymity was upheld; participants' personal information remained confidential, and no identifiable details were disclosed without consent. Lastly, the researchers communicated any potential risks—whether physical, emotional, or psychological—and implemented appropriate measures to mitigate those risks. By diligently addressing these ethical considerations, the researchers maintained the integrity of their work and protected the rights and welfare of the participants.

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